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YOUTH PROBLEMS IN THE MODERN FAMILY

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ABSTRACT

This article highlights the issues of identifying and solving the main socio-economic problems of young families. Particular attention is paid to expanding the legislative and legal framework for the development of assistance to young families, as well as the need for a systematic approach to the issue of comprehensive support for young families.

Young families are among the most important socio-economic problems in society the study of related issues deserves special attention. In our country formation of a healthy lifestyle in the family, comprehensive support and protection of family relations from a socio-ethical point of view; attention is being paid. After all, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev has noted, "... the family in today's rapidly changing age of conflict without studying the issues on a scientific basis, many people in social life find it difficult to find answers to complex questions».

It has been polished in this place for centuries correctly understanding the coming national values failure, social, universal rules personal distortion by men being understood, not fully fulfilling the role of women in emotional-intimate relations between husband and wife, Under the influence of stereotypes, the behavior of women inconsistent with their nature remains the cause of gender inequality and discrimination. Gender of spouses in Uzbek families the issue of equality is somewhat controversial and it is psychogenetic, psychophysiological, psychophysiological, explained by the presence of socio-psychological, national-ethnic factors. Spouses with developed emotional and psychological harmony see each other as beloved people in their feelings. Mutually idealized perception, beautiful, intelligent, positive and perceptive qualities was determined. Expressing mutual altruism, feelings of cuteness prevail in married couples was observed.

One of the next problems in the modern family is divorce. Therefore, family disputes have become an actual problem today. Although the family is the sacred place of support of a person, some young couples are unable to maintain their family relationship. Divorce is chosen as a solution to problems. In 2020, 296,934 marriages were registered in Uzbekistan, while the number of divorces was 28,254. This means that one out of every 10 newly created families was divorced. In 2010, the number of divorces was 17,794, which shows that the dynamics of

growth is quite high. International organizations, in particular, the UN, annually provide the global coefficient of divorce. According to these data, divorce statistics are changing dramatically due to a number of influential factors. Divorce around the world is heavily influenced by marital discord, infidelity, drug/alcohol addiction, financial deprivation, and physical/emotional abuse.

Also, factors such as the intervention of third parties, mother-in-law relations, childlessness, young families not having their own housing and source of income have a great impact on the divorce of Uzbek families. Divorces usually have a variety of reasons, some very minor and others not. What is important to one divorcing couple may not be important to another. Regardless of the reason, divorce is not a pleasant situation, it has many disadvantages for the family and society. Divorce is painful for children. Many children feel that they blame themselves for their parents' divorce, and that guilt causes sadness. Divorce has a negative impact on children's education, leading to a slowdown in the learning process or limited financial resources for educational opportunities.

Economic damage. Divorce has a negative impact on the financial lifestyle of families. Livelihood divided between two persons is borne by one person. According to international statistics, every fifth divorced woman falls into poverty, and every third woman becomes homeless. Most men's standard of living will drop by 10-40 percent. This situation, in turn, affects the development of society and causes the growth of poverty and the increase of people in need of social assistance. Two blocks of the most urgent problems from the point of view of young families it is necessary to distinguish: socio-economic and socio-psychological.

The first block provides material support, housing and employment for young spouses includes supply problems. In most cases, there are few young families well-off and most are below the poverty line. Youth in the labor market due to the lack of demand for a specialist or the lack of relevant work experience low salaries lead to deterioration of the financial situation of young families and in general helps to lower the standard of living of the country's population. The second block brings young spouses to each other, to a new situation (changing roles, stereotypes and behavior style) and new includes problems of adaptation to relatives.

A number of researchers have analyzed the current situation of a young family, in addition to social and everyday problems of the modern family problems of stability, problems of family education, endangered they offer to consider the problems of families. In general, the main factors affecting family problems and the current situation of a young family includes a low level of family income; own lack of housing; increased risk of poverty; family life of young people not ready; ignorance of its moral and psychological foundations; resolve disputes not to receive; selfishness. Spouses are a very important problem for a young family inconsistency of the hierarchy of values. So, a number of young families there are problems. The main ones are material, household and housing problems; psychological problems; the problem of employment of young spouses. These problems so that a young family can fulfill all its functions A comprehensive solution is necessary, the focus of the state family policy on this young family should be in the center.

To strengthen families, especially young families today the more attention is paid, the modern society that is being built and the democratic state continues to develop. In the

relations of young families economic, social, spiritual and psychological processes it is necessary to study and analyze more deeply. The family has its functions failure to do so may result in various deviations.

The uniqueness of the young family is to solve its problems and the young family to allocate as a separate object of the state youth and family policy requires a special approach, which in turn with this social group it should be reflected in the implementation of social work. Most of the young families live as a result of receiving low wages a decrease in the level is observed. Lack of funds is a problem for many people causing families to forgo health services because most health care facilities have switched to fee-based services. to theaters, visiting concert halls, resorts and holiday homes, Children's and wellness camps are also accessible to many young families no. Due to low income, the purchasing power of young families is reduced and they are low forced to buy quality products and products, as a result life affects the quality.

Science - science and the public to study the problems of a young family in depth and interested in finding optimal ways to solve them. Any The main difficulties of a young family in society are, first of all, a person's low professional position and woman not working due to childbirth, age without work experience lack of demand for specialists, caused by unemployment difficulties. Second, a separate housing problem. Of course, together such obstacles are encountered at the initial stage of living. Young family One of the dominant problems is the housing problem. This issue several scientific works have been done and many scientific articles have been written, but to solve the problem, a lot of money and state, society and social systematic participation of responsible business is required.

General crisis of modern young families in developed countries Another problem is demographic problems. In young families the decline in fertility has become the main problem in family relations is going This is the result of scientific research conducted by scientists shows that girls who get married early have financial support for their families and spiritual dependence, loneliness, mental imbalance, there are many situations like impressionability. In addition to an independent life not being ready to fully understand the responsibilities and obligations of young families causes not enough. This is different from dissatisfaction with life in young families causes problems.

In general, the well-being of young families will improve it is necessary to pay sufficient attention to the following issues:

- Formation of young families and their life in modern conditions more in-depth study and analysis of the style through sociological research reach;
- General theory of family-marital relations in young families objective and subjective factors in the complex from modern ideas analysis based on;
- In determining the formation of personality and family harmony in a young family study of the decisive role of the family based on scientifically accurate data reach;

Economic, family-marital relations in young families more theoretical aspects of social and psychological processes in all aspects a deeper study and analysis is an important necessity. Market economy In the process, take into account the socio-economic status and lifestyle of young families taking effective measures to protect them socially should be developed.

The problems of young families, the contradictions that exist in them, special regional for continuous monitoring of achievements and shortcomings a sociological center should be established. In our opinion, young families A systematic approach plays an important role in the study of family relations.

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